

Spectrophotometric determination of nickel at microgram level in environmental matrices using 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone

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Abstract : The reagent 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (4-HBTS) has been synthesized, characterised and its analytical applications were investigated. The reagent 4-HBTS reacts with Ni^{II} in aqueous solution in the pH range 5–6 at room temperature and forms a green coloured 1 : 2 [Ni^{II} : 4-HBTS] complex with stability constant 2.76×10^{11} . The complex has maximum absorption at 362 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for the coloured solution are found to be $2.13 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0027 \text{ } \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ respectively. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0.117–1.117 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The interference of various diverse ions has been studied. The procedure was successfully applied for the determination of nickel in water, waste water samples and in different alloy samples.

Keywords : Nickel determination, spectrophotometry, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, waste water, alloy samples.

Introduction

Nickel is versatile metal in biological chemistry. It has been reported that normal human blood plasma contains 0.012–0.085 ppm of Ni^{II}. Nickel is abundant in lithosphere and biosphere. Nickel is widely used in electroplating, in the manufacture of Ni-Cd batteries, rods for arc welding, pigments of paints, ceramic surgical and dental prostheses, computer components, magnetic tapes and nickel catalysts. Nickel enters in to the water from dissolution of industrial process and waste disposal¹. Nickel was thought to be essential for plants and some domestic animals², but not considered to be a metal of biological importance until 1975, when Zerner discovered that urease was a nickel enzyme³. Nickel is moderately toxic metal, and still at low concentrations produces a general toxic effect on the human organism causing nasopharynx and lung diseases, malignant tumors and dermatological diseases⁴. Nickel containing sewage water is harm full after ingress in to water. Flame and graphite furnace atomic

absorption spectrometry and spectrophotometric methods provides accurate and rapid determination of nickel in water and waste water⁵.

Thiosemicarbazones are good analytical reagents^{6–10}. Several thiosemicarbazones have been employed as chromogenic reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of nickel^{11–16}. Some of them are less sensitive^{11,12} and less selective^{13,14} while others involve extraction in to carcinogenic organic solvents^{15,16}. In this present note a simple, selective and sensitive spectrophotometric method was developed for the determination of nickel in water, industrial waste water and in different alloys using 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone.

Experimental

The absorbance and pH measurements were made on a Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer (model UV-160A) fitted with 1.0 cm quartz cells and Elico digital pH meter (model LI20) respectively.

Preparation and characterization of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone :

(i) Preparation of 4-HBTS :

The reagent was prepared by simple condensation of 1 mole of 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.22 g) with 1 mole (0.92 g) of thiosemicarbazide in a clean 250 mL round bottomed flask, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde was dissolved in 100 mL of methanol and thiosemicarbazide was dissolved in hot water. The solutions were mixed and refluxed for two hours. On cooling brown colored product was formed which was collected by filtration. It was recrystallized using methanol and dried in vacuum. The yield was 80% by weight and the m.p. was 207–209 °C. The structure of the compound was established using IR spectra and NMR spectra.

Characterization :

The IR spectrum of the compound was recorded using Perkin-Elmer 1371 R spectrometer in KBr. The peaks observed at 3458 cm^{-1} and 3342 cm^{-1} may be assigned to symmetric and asymmetric (-N-H) stretching frequency of primary amino group. The peak observed at 3028 cm^{-1} may be assigned to Ar-H stretching frequency of aromatic proton, and that observed at 1595 cm^{-1} to C=N stretching frequency of azomethine. The peak observed at 3218–3092 for -OH group. A strong peak observed at 1056 cm^{-1} may be assigned to C=S stretching frequency. The peaks observed in the range of 1530–1360 cm^{-1} frequency were characteristic aromatic ring stretching frequency.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of the compound was recorded with DRX300 NMR spectrometer in DMF solvent. The peak observed at δ value 10.74 (H) was characteristic of phenolic -OH group. The peak found at δ value 7.86

(4H) may be due to aromatic protons, the peak observed at δ value 6.8 (2H) may be due to -NH₂ protons attached to thionyl group (C=S) and the peak observed at δ value 9.0 is due to aldehydic proton. The peak at δ value 11.5 may be due to -NH proton (azomethine).

Preparation of the solutions :

Ni^{II} solution :

0.5942 g of nickel sulphate (A.R., BDH) was dissolved in doubly distilled water containing few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ and made upto 250 mL. The stock solution was standardized gravimetrically using dimethylglyoxime. The stock solution was suitably diluted to get the required concentration.

Stock solution of the reagent :

0.195 g of recrystallised sample of the reagent 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was dissolved in DMF in a 100 mL volumetric flask to obtain the stock solution (0.1 M), and it was suitably diluted to get the required concentration. Fresh reagent solutions were prepared as and when required.

Buffer solutions :

The buffer solutions are prepared by mixing 1 M hydrochloric acid and 1 M sodium acetate (pH 1.0–3.0) and 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M sodium acetate (pH 3.5–7.0). Exact pH of the solution was measured using a pH meter.

Results and discussion

Ni^{II} reacts with 4-HBTS in weak acidic pH to give a green coloured water soluble species. The colour reaction between Ni^{II} and 4-HBTS is instantaneous even at room temperature. The absorption spectra of 4-HBTS with water blank and its nickel(II) complex under the optimum conditions are as shown in the Fig. 1. The nickel(II)-4-HBTS complex shows the maximum absorbance at 400 nm, where the reagent blank does not absorb appreciably. The maximum absorbance λ_{max} of the green coloured species (complex) was observed at 400 nm which remains constant for 24 h. Studies on the effect of pH on the absorbance revealed that the maximum colour was formed in a solution of pH 6. A ten fold excess of the reagent is adequate for complete colour development. Addition of excess of reagent has no adverse effect on absorbance.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of Ni^{II}-4-HBTS.

The studies relating to the effect of Ni^{II} revealed that a linear relationship exists between metal ion concentration and the absorbance (Fig. 2) in the range 0.117–1.172 µg/mL. The molar absorptivity and Sandell’s sensitivity are $2.13 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $2.76 \times 10^{-3} \text{ µg/cm}^2$ respectively. The effect of the reagent on absorbance is also studied, no linear relationship is found between the reagent and the absorbance. As the metal ion Ni^{II} forms a coloured complex with reagent, an attempt is made to determine the composition and the stability of the complex. Job’s method and mole ratio method are conducted

to make these determinations. It is noticed that Ni^{II} forms a stable green coloured 1 : 2 [M : L] complex with 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone. The stability constant of the complex was found to be 2.76×10^{11} . Data related various parameters of Ni^{II}-4-HBTS complex is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Physico-chemical and analytical characteristics of Ni^{II}-4-HBTS

Characteristics	Results
λ_{max} (nm)	400
pH range (optimum)	5.0–6.0
Moles of the reagent required per mole of metal ion for complete colour development	10-folds
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	2.13×10^4
Sandell’s sensitivity (µg/cm^2)	2.76×10^{-3}
Standard deviation in the determination of 1.17 µg/ml of Ni ^{VI} for ten determinations	0.00152
RSD (%)	0.13
Regression equation	$A_{362} = 0.0223C - 0.0033$
Beer’s law validity range (µg/ml)	0.117–1.172
Composition of the complex (M : L) obtained in Job’s and mole ratio method	1 : 2
Stability constant	2.76×10^{11}

Fig. 2. Beer’s law verification.

Influence of various cations and anions on the absorbance values is studied. The tolerance limit in each case is expressed in $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The data pertaining to the above studies is presented in the Table 2.

Table 2. Tolerance limit of foreign ions in the determination of 1.1742 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ nickel

Ion added (Anions)	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Ion added (Cations)	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Thiourea	315	Mo^{VI}	19.24
Chloride	212.7	Manganese(II)	3.8
Bromide	319.6	Iron(II)	2.0
Iodide	560	Zinc(II)	1.22
Nitrate	400	Silver(I)	2.15
Acetate	590	Copper(II) ^a	1.70
Urea	288	Vanadium(V)	12.2
Tartarate	883	Chromium(VI)	2.5

^aIn the presence of 315 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of thiourea.

The cations chosen exhibit the same physical and chemical properties as that of the metal ion. Most of the anions do not show much interference, while cations like iron(II), zinc(II) and silver(I) interfere seriously in the determination of nickel.

Furthermore, a comparison of analytical parameter obtained by this method and with that reported by several other spectrophotometric methods for the determination of nickel is given in the Table 3.

Applications of the proposed method :

To confirm the usefulness of the proposed method, it was applied to the determination of nickel in ground water and in industrial waste water samples. For this purpose the water samples were collected from different parts of industrial estate in Anantapuram, Andhra Pradesh. The water samples (1 liter) were collected in clean 2 liter beakers and slowly evaporated to 25 mL; then 5 ml of H_2O_2 was added and evaporated to dryness. It was then dissolved in 20 mL of water and filtered to remove insoluble substance. The filtrate was collected in 100 mL volumetric flask quantitatively and diluted to the mark with distilled water. Two untreated waste water samples collected from different parts of industrial estate in Anantapuram, Andhra Pradesh have been analysed after treating the water sample using the procedure described above. Reliability of the method was checked by the spiking experiments and comparing the results with the data obtained by GF-AAS as shown in the Table 4, the results obtained with the proposed method agree well with data obtained by furnace atomic absorption analysis and the recovery of the spiked sample is good, suggesting that the procedure is reliable for sample examination.

Determination of Ni^{II} in different alloys :

Alloy material (0.4 g) was treated with 15 mL of 1 : 1 HCl. To this 3 ml of HNO_3 was added and the contents

Table 3. Comparison of present method with other reported spectrophotometric methods

Reagent	pH	λ_{max} (nm)	Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	Beer's law range (ppm/ $\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Ref.
Oxamidoxime	3.0–5.0	233	21.0×10^3	1–30	17
Furyl- α -dioxime	Acidic	435	14.5×10^3	1.0–20.0	18
Benzil- α -dioxime	8.0–11.4	275	12.0×10^3	1.0–20.0	19
Nicotinamidoxime	11.0	575	4.2×10^3	0.3–10	20
4-Tetrabutylcyclohexane-1,2-dionedioxime	7.0	386	4.1×10^3	0.55–17	21
Isovanillin thiosemicarbazone	9.0	400	6.4×10^3	2.0–20.0	22
Biacetylmonoxime-4-phenyl-2-thiosemicarbazone	5.2–10.0	375	17.1×10^3	0.5–2.5	23
2-Hydroxy-4-isopropoxy acetophenone thiosemicarbazone	9.0	400	8.4×10^2	16.44	24
Pyridoxial-4-phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone	4–6	430	1.92×10^4	0.5–5.0	25
N-Ethyl-3-carbazole carboxaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone	6.0	400	1.114×10^4	1.2–5.6	26
4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone	6.0	400	2.13×10^4	0.117–1.172	Present method

Table 4. Determination of nickel in ground water and in industrial waste water samples

Sample	Added ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Recovery (%)	GF-AAS ^a ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Ground water	15.0	ND ^b	98.7	5.3 \pm 0.2
		14.7 \pm 0.3		
Industrial waste water (1)	15.0	76.2 \pm 0.8	96	75.6 \pm 1.8
		90.6 \pm 1.3		
Industrial waste water (2)	15.0	68.3 \pm 1.2	94	67.8 \pm 1.2
		82.5 \pm 1.4		

^aMean and standard deviation of three determinations, ^bND – Not determined.

boiled until dissolution was complete, then 10 mL of water and 40 mL of 4 N NH₄OH solution were added and filtered through a Whatman filter paper (no. 41). The filtrate was collected in to 25 mL volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water. Known aliquots of the above sample solution were taken in 10 ml flask containing 5 ml buffer solution (pH 6), 883 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ tartarate (to mask Fe^{II}) and 315 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of thiourea (to mask Cu^{II}) and 1 mL of 4-HBTS solution (5×10^{-3} M). The contents were made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 362 nm against reagent blank. The amount of Ni^{II} present in the sample solution was determined from the predetermined calibration plot. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Determination of nickel in alloy samples

Sample	Nickel(%)		Error (%)
	Certified	Found*	
BCS-CRM 38T ^a	41.90	41.10	-1.9
Monel 400 ^b	63.01	64.00	1.6
Oa Kay ^c	60.00	59.20	-1.3

*Average of five determinations.

Composition of the alloys :

- (a) 41.9% Ni; 36% Fe; 12.46% Cr; 5.83% Mo; 2.95% Ti; 0.28% Se; 0.29% Al; 0.21% Co; 0.08% Mn; 0.092% Cu.
 (b) 63.01% Ni; 0.15% C; 0.0024% S; 0.07% Mn; 0.5% Si; 2.5% Fe; 31.0% Cu.
 (c) 60.00% Ni; 20.00% Pt; 9.5% V; 10.5% Pd.

Conclusions

The methods described in this paper allows for the rapid, precise and reliable determination of nickel in water, industrial waste water and in some alloy samples. The main benefits of the procedure are the enhanced sensitivity of the spectrophotometric method, low cost, fairly easy operation and speed of analysis.

References

1. E. Merian, M. Anke and M. Stoppler, "Elements and their compounds in the environment", Vol. 2, Wiley, VCH, Weinheim, 2004.
2. K. Wand, "Nickel, Trace elements in life sciences", Chinese Measurement Press, Peking, 1991.
3. B. Zerner, *Bioorg. Chem.*, 1991, **19**, 116.
4. D. Templeton, "Biological monitoring of chemical exposure in the work place", World Health Organization, Geneva, 1990.
5. M. A. H. Franson, "Standard methods for examination of water and waste water", American Publication Health Association, Washington, DC, USA, 1995.
6. T. S. Lobana, Rekha Sharma, Gagandeep Bawa and Sonia Khanna, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **253**, 977.
7. Jessicachan, Amber L., Thomson, Michale W. Jones and Josephine M. Pech, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 1140.
8. B. Prathima, Y. Subba Rao, S. Adinarayana Reddy, Y. P. Reddy and A. Varada Reddy, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2010, **77**, 248.
9. Javier Garcia Tojal, Jose Pizarro, Africa Garecia-Orad, Ana Rocio Peroz-Saz, Maria Ugalde, Antonia Alvarezdiaz, Jaun Luis Serra, Maria Isabel Arriortus and Teofilo Roio, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2001, **86**, 627.
10. El Mostapha Jouad, Amedeerio, Magali Allain, Mustayeen A. Khan and Gilles M. Bouet, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 67.
11. S. L. C. Ferreira, B. F. Santos, J. B. de Andrade and A. C. Spinola Costa, *Microchim. Acta*, 1996, **122**, 109.
12. A. K. Malik, K. N. Kaul, B. S. Lark, W. Faube and A. L. J. Rao, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 99.
13. A. Kumar and M. Jain, *Chem. Anal.*, 1992, **39**, 73.
14. A. K. Bansal and M. Nagar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 731.
15. S. N. Boladani, M. Tewari, A. Agarwal and K. C. Sekhan, *Fr. J. Anal. Chem.*, 1994, **349**, 478.
16. T. Odashima, K. Kohata, K. Yogi and H. Ishi, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1995, **44**, 135.
17. F. D. Shell, "Photometric methods of analysis", John Wiley, New York, 1978.

18. R. M. Garcia, M. L. Alvarez, M. T. F. Fernandez and M. J. A. Garcia, *Anales de Quimic*, 1991, **87**, 626.
19. Y. M. Issa, M. S. Rizk and S. J. Mohammed, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **74**, 128.
20. Y. Y. Zhu, J. H. Liu, P. Liu and X. J. Zhou, *Mikrochimica Acta*, 1993, **112**, 127.
21. N. Shukla, G. J. Pandey and J. K. Maitra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 793.
22. Y. M. Issa, M. S. Rizk, H. A. Mohammed and S. I. Mohammed, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 128.
23. I. Blazys, R. Jurevicius, P. Vanilavicius and M. M. Burbulieve, *Chemica*, 1996, **53**.
24. V. K. Desai and K. K. Desai, *Orient. J. Chem.*, 1996, **12**, 203.
25. Loka Subramanyam, Jyothi Rajesh Kumar, Koduru Janardhana Reddy, Thenepalli Thriveni and Ammireddy Varada Reddy, *Journal of Trace Elements in Medicine and Biology*, 2008, **22**, 285.
26. C. Ramachandraiah, J. Rajesh Kumar, K. Janardhana Reddy, S. Lakshmi Narayana and A. Varada Reddy, *Journal of Environmental Management*, 2008, **88**, 729.